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Acute toxicity and antihyperlipidemic activity of polyherbal formulation in poloxamer-induced hyperlipidemic mice model

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses acute toxicity and antihyperlipidemic activity of a new polyherbal preparation, CHM-Lipid. It was developed based on the traditional use of indigenous plants *Celastrus hindsii*, *Curcuma zedoaria*, *Docynia indica*, *Hibiscus sabdariffa*, and *Lactuca indica* in Vietnam. The acute toxicity was evaluated following the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) guidelines No. 423 using six lots of BALB/c albino mice. The antihyperlipidemic activity: Total Cholesterol (TC), Triglyceride (TG), Low-Density Lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), and High-Density Lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) was studied using Poloxamer 407 (P-407) induced hyperlipidemia mice model on 25 Swiss albino mice of either sex. The mice fasted overnight were divided into three control groups, namely negative control given intraperitoneally injected isotonic saline, positive control given P-407, and given P-407 and treated with the standard drug. Two groups were induced with P-407 and treated with different doses of CHM-Lipid at 500 and 1,000 mg/kgP. The acute toxicity analysis showed that CHM-Lipid was orally non-toxic at a single dose of 5,000 mg/kgP. It did not cause any pre-clinical changes in experimental animals. The results of the antihyperlipidemic

study showed that CHM-Lipid exhibited noticeable antihyperlipidemic activity in the P-407-induced mice model at the 500 mg/kgP dose with significantly lowered TC, TG, and LDL-C values. These findings suggest that CHM-Lipid could be a promising candidate for the development of new antihyperlipidemic drugs and suggest that CHM-Lipid may serve as a safe and effective antihyperlipidemic polyherbal combination.

Keywords: acute toxicity, antihyperlipidemic activity, indigenous plants, polyherbal preparation, southwest region of Vietnam

1. INTRODUCTION

Hyperlipidemia is commonly defined as an increase in TC concentration that might result in elevated LDL-C and high TG levels (Vallejo-Vaz et al. 2017; Alves et al. 2024). These abnormalities in lipid profile have been proven to be the greatest risk factor for atherosclerosis and secondary cardiovascular disease, a leading cause of death in many countries (Kim et al. 2019). Hyperlipidemia, either genetic or acquired, is caused by high-fat food intake, a secondary effect of diabetes mellitus, and requires strict treatment and ongoing lipid-lowering medication (Ida et al. 2022). For the last decades, many studies have been conducted to develop new drugs that help to regulate hyperlipidemia (Lluís et al. 2023). In its treatment, simvastatin inhibitors and HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors have been used. However, they had side effects (Rasyad et al. 2020). Recently, natural products, medicinal plants, and herbal formulations have been popularly used for hyperlipidemia treatment because they minimize the side effects. In vivo trials showed that *Trigonella foenum-graecum* seeds had good activity on rabbits-induced hyperlipidemia, *Aloe megalacantha* leaves had good antidiabetic and antihyperlipidemic activities in streptozotocin-induced diabetic mice, *Annona reticulata* leaves had good antidiabetic in streptozotocin-induced diabetic mice, etc. (Sharma et al. 2016; Hammeso et al. 2019; Wen et al. 2019; Okokon et al. 2022).

In Vietnam, some natural products and medicinal plants have shown good biological activities, including lipid-lowering medication (Pham. 2024). There are few effective antihyperlipidemia therapies available that were not toxic in both pre-clinical and clinical trials. Utilizing animal models for toxicity testing is a time-honored practice. However, in vivo animal experimentation is restricted due to time constraints, ethical concerns, and financial constraints.

Therefore, the creation of novel and safe medications is needed to treat antihyperlipidemia. In the continuance of the global fight against cardiovascular diseases, this research focuses on the plant-derived antihyperlipidemic formulation, so-called CHM-Lipid, from local medicinal plants in the southwestern region of Vietnam: *C. hindsii*, *C. zedoaria*, *D. indica*, *H. sabdariffa*, and *L. indica*. The ingredients in the polyherbal formulation were selected based on an indigenous medicine that is further scientifically validated in this study by extraction and proven antihypercholesterolemic properties. *C. hindsii* was reported to be rich in triterpenes, alkaloids, and flavonoids and, therefore, exhibited strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities in several studies (Huy et al. 2020). *C. hindsii* is commonly used in Vietnamese traditional medicine as a cancer-inhibiting and hepatitis-treating factor (Thanh et al. 2020; Thi et al. 2020).

C. zedoaria belongs to the family *Zingiberaceae* which is commonly cultivated over Asia. As far as it has been discussed in food or medicinal use, many studies supported *Curcuma*

zedoaria's antioxidant, antimicrobial, and antihypercholesterolemic properties. Zedoary tea was also reported to have a lipid-lowering effect on mild hypercholesterolemic volunteers after 60 days of consumption (Gharge et al. 2021). *D. indica* is a wild edible plant but is now widely cultivated in Vietnam. *D. Indica* fruits have been traditionally used as a supplemental remedy to stimulate digestion and treat different diseases. In recent studies, *D. indica* fruits presented antihyperlipidemic properties (Biswas et al. 2022; Zhang et al. 2018). *H. sabdariffa* is native to Southeast Asia. The ethanolic *H. sabdariffa* extract showed reducing control over TC, LDL-C, and atherogenic index as effectively as lovastatin, a cholesterol-lowering agent, in the alloxan-induced rat model (Zhang et al. 2019; Farombi et al. 2007). *L. indica* is a wild edible plant that can be found in many places in Vietnam. It contains valuable nutrients such as polyphenols, sterols, and vitamins and is traditionally used for hypertension and cardiac disease treatment. Some *in vivo* experiments showed the hypolipidemic effect of *L. indica* by reducing TC and TG levels (Salih. 2019).

All plants mentioned above are indigenous to Vietnam, and their combinations with each other have been commonly used in traditional remedies for cholesterol-reducing purposes. However, potential concerns of toxicity and pharmaceutical effects need to be resolved for further development of such a multicomponent herbal formulation. Thus, in this study, we directed our attention to the assessment of the acute toxicity and antihyperlipidemic activity of the polyherbal combination, which has not been scientifically authenticated.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Chemicals and reagents

Poloxamer 407 (P-407) and atorvastatin (10 mg tablet) from Sigma Aldrich (USA) were obtained from Central Pharmaceutical CPC1 JSC., Vietnam, and other reagents and chemicals were with analytical grade from Merck (USA). Enzymatic commercial kits for TC, TG, LDL-C, and HDL-C were obtained from Linear Chemicals Ltd (Spain).

2. 2. Procedures

2. 2. 1. Preparation of ingredient extracts and polyherbal formulation

The herbal materials for extract preparation, *D. indica* and *L. indica*, were purchased at Ninh Hiep Commune Medicinal Plants Market in Hanoi (Hanoi), while *C. hindsii*, *C. zedoaria* and *H. sabdariffa* were collected from An Giang province (Vietnam). All the studied samples were authenticated by Dr. Hai T.V. (VAST).

Among those, *C. zedoaria* and *L. indica* extracts were prepared according to standard methods of Vietnamese Pharmacopeia V (Ministry of Health. 2019). Other ingredient extracts were prepared following laboratory-developed methods (Hung LN 2020, unpublished data). Each hard capsule sized 0 contains 80 mg *C. hindsii* extract, 120 mg *C. zedoaria* extract, 100 mg *D. indica* fruit extract, 120 mg *H. sabdariffa* extract, 80 mg *L. indica* extract, and sufficient excipients.

2. 2. 2. Experimental animals

BALB/c albino mice and Swiss albino mice of either sex, weighing 19 to 22 grams, were obtained and kept in the animal house of the Pharmacy University of Hanoi. Experimental mice

were kept in the standard laboratory conditions at 25 ± 2 °C, relative humidity of 44-56%, and 12:12 hours light and dark cycles and maintained 5 days before the experiment, freely fed with standard diet and water. The design and performance of animal experiments were approved by the Ethical Committee, Pharmacy University of Hanoi, Vietnam (reference number 3-22/PCT-HDDĐ).

2. 3. Experimental procedures

2. 3. 1. Acute oral toxicity study

The acute toxicity experiments followed the OECD guideline No. 423 (OECD No. 423, 2001). The healthy BALB/c albino mice were fasted for 16 hours before the commencement of experiments. Groups were fed, designed, and observed for body weight and behavior before and after oral administration on days 1, 4, and 7th of the experiment. Administration of the stepwise dose of polyherbal preparation CHM-Lipid from 1,000 mg/kgP up to 5,000 mg/kgP was picked due to the results of the exploratory pre-test.

Lot 1 (one mouse): was given 10% ethanol at 0.3- 0.4 ml as normal control,

Lot 2 (one mouse): was given CHM-Lipid at a dose of 1000 mg/kgP. If no mortality occurs, testing proceeds to a further stage,

Lot 3 (six mice): were given CHM-Lipid at a dose of 2,000 mg/kgP,

Lot 4 (six mice): were given CHM-Lipid at a dose of 3,000 mg/kgP,

Lot 5 (six mice): were given CHM-Lipid at a dose of 4,000 mg/kgP,

Lot 6 (six mice): were given CHM-Lipid at a dose of 5,000 mg/kgP.

2. 3. 2. Hyperlipidemic induced model

The experiments on antihyperlipidemic activity in the P-407-induced hyperlipidemia mice model were conducted following a previously described hyperlipidemia induction protocol with slight modification (Kim et al., 2016). A fructose diet was administered at 3 mL daily. The mice were divided into 5 groups randomly of 5 as follows:

Lot 1 presented negative control and was given water and intraperitoneally injected with isotonic saline,

Lot 2 presented positive control, was given water, and induced with Poloxamer 407,

Lot 3 was induced with P-407 and treated with atorvastatin (50 mg/kg) as the standard drug,

Lot 4 was induced with P-407 and treated with polyherbal formulation at 500 mg/kgP/day,

Lot 5 was induced intraperitoneally with P-407 and treated with polyherbal formulation at 1000 mg/kgP.

All hyperlipidemia-induced groups were given a single dose of 600 mg/kgP of 30% P-407 in water (w/v) by intraperitoneal (i.p.) injection. Two hours after P-407 administration, each group was given either water, atorvastatin, or polyherbal preparation.

2. 3. 3. Blood sampling

Next, 24 hours after injection, all experimental animals were fasted overnight. Blood samples were collected for each mouse after they were anesthetized with diethyl ether from the retro-orbital plexus and incubated at room temperature for 30 minutes. The blood samples were centrifuged for 10 min at 4,000 rpm at 4 °C, and the serum was separated and stored at -40 °C until it was used for biochemical tests.

2. 3. 4. Biochemical estimations of lipid profile

Blood samples were evaluated for TC, TG, LDL-C, and HDL-C; the levels of these substances in the serum were estimated using commercial kits enzymatic colorimetric methods.

2. 4. Data analysis

All data presented in this study are expressed as the mean, standard deviation of the mean value (S.E.M). Statistical analysis consisted of the Student's t-test for comparing two mean values and a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) when more than two mean values were compared.

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Acute toxicity study

While administrating CHM-Lipid powder at all doses, there was no dizziness, piloerection, or lethargy. Loss of appetite was observed in one mouse of lot 4 dosing within 30 minutes that lasted only for the first day. After seven days of experiment, experimental animals displayed no behavioral changes or toxic signs, and no death was observed in any groups of mice. Attention was given to body weight evaluation before and during the experiment period, as presented in Table 1. A slight increase in body weight was seen after seven days in all the lots. The increase in weight of the control group, lot 1, was compared to the other animal groupings using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). There was not significant ($P > 0.05$) increase in weight of all groups compared to the control group.

Table 1. Weight evaluation of body weight in mice.

Lot/dose (mg/kg)	Body weight (g)			
	Before administration	Day 1	Day 4	Day 7
Lot 1/ control	20.63 ± 0.27	20.67 ± 0.39	21.87 ± 0.32	22.95 ± 0.26
Lot 2/ 1000 mg/kgP	20.71 ± 0.30	20.70 ± 0.27	21.93 ± 0.41	23.05 ± 0.26
Lot 3/ 2000 mg/kgP	20.48 ± 0.25	20.51 ± 0.32	21.63 ± 0.38	21.76 ± 0.30
Lot 4/ 3000 mg/kgP	20.62 ± 0.31	20.63 ± 0.26	22.63 ± 0.33	22.78 ± 0.28
Lot 5/ 4000 mg/kgP	20.47 ± 0.28	20.50 ± 0.35	21.56 ± 0.24	22.49 ± 0.33
Lot 6/ 5000 mg/kgP	20.57 ± 0.34	20.54 ± 0.32	21.53 ± 0.30	22.52 ± 0.42
<i>P</i>	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05

* $P < 0.05$ means that the difference is statistically significant.

Overall, the results showed that at a dose of 5,000 mg/kgP, the polyherbal formulation was non-toxic and did not cause any abnormal clinical changes in tested animals.

3. 2. Antihyperlipidemic activity study

Table 2 presents changes in the lipid profile of induced mice from the normal group 24 hours after the administration of P-407.

Table 2. Various lipid parameters of mice in different experimental groups.

No	Group	TC (mmol/L)	TG (mmol/L)	HDL – C (mmol/L)	LDL – C (mmol/L)
1	Group 1 - normal mice	2.87 ± 0.14	1.46 ± 0.08	1.21 ± 0.05	0.93 ± 0.05
2	Group 2 - hyperlipidemia induced	14.07 ± 0.19	15.66 ± 0.29	2.45 ± 0.18	7.24 ± 0.23
3	Group 3 - atorvastatin: 50 mg/kgP	8.64* ± 0.15 (↓39.02)	8.11* ± 0.08 (↓48.20)	2.82 ± 0.09 (↑12.94%)	5.03* ± 0.10 (↓30.54%)
4	Group 4 - CHM-Lipid: 500 mg/kgP	9.66* ± 0.21 (↓31.37%)	10.70* ± 0.29 (↓31.63%)	2.64 ± 0.10 (↑6.87%)	5.52* ± 0.17 (↓23.77%)
5	Group 5 - CHM-Lipid: 1000 mg/kgP	12.82 ± 0.25 (↓8.91%)	14.82 ± 0.21 (↓5.33%)	2.28 ± 0.08 (↓7.21%)	6.72 ± 0.26 (↓7.23%)

* Statistically significant difference P < 0.05 from control groups.

Our findings have significant implications for the field of pharmacology and veterinary medicine. The daily supplementation of fasted diet pellets for animals in group 2 (P-407 hyperlipidemic-induced mice without treatment) led to a significant increase in lipid levels of all studied parameters: TC levels by 490.24%, TG levels by 1,072.60%, and LDL-C by 202.48% (P<0.05) compared to group 1 (normal control) indicating that administration of a fasted diet was enough to induce a state of hyperlipidemia in mice. Similar elevated lipid levels were also observed in the other treatment groups after the induction period. Animals induced and treated with the standard lipid-lowering drug, atorvastatin, showed a significant decline in TC levels by 39.02%, TG levels by 38.20%, and LDL-C levels by 30.54% but a rise in HDL-C levels by 12.94% in comparison with group 1. Similarly to atorvastatin, at a dose of 500 mg/kgP/day, CHM-Lipid significantly lowered TC values by 31.37 %, TG values by 31.63%, and LDL-C values by 23.77 % and slightly rose HDL-C levels by 6.87% levels but the last one wasn't statistically significant when compared to the positive control P 407-induced treatment group 3. However, at a higher dose of 1,000 mg/kgP of CHM-Lipid administration, the decrease in TC values by 8.91%, TG values by 5.33%, and LDL-C values by 7.23% was statistically significant (P<0.05) when compared with the P 407-induced treatment group 3. Thus, the polyherbal combination possessed the lipid-lowering effect, suggesting potential new avenues for lipid-lowering therapies.

4. DISCUSSION

The herbal medicines safety evaluation is essential for determining the negative effects these formulations may have on humans. In addition, it is a fundamental component of the therapy design procedure before the study of any pharmaceutical activities (Aydın et al. 2022). In the acute toxicity study, no dead mouse was found after taking CHM-Lipid preparation in all experimental and control groups, underscoring its non-toxic nature. Even a high dose of 5,000 mg/kgP did not cause any abnormal clinical changes in tested mice. According to OECD, Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS), and WHO classification based on oral toxicity, the studied polyherbal formulation was non-toxic at maximum doses, with a median lethal dose $LD_{50} > 5,000$ mg/kg body weight, could be considered non-toxic or unclassified. Previously, each constituent of the new formulation, CHM-Lipid, had been studied for acute toxicity.

Each herbal component of the polyherbal formulation, CHM-Lipid, has not been shown to be acutely toxic in acute toxicity research. The single oral administration of aqueous extract of *C. hindsii* at a dose of 15,000 mg/kgP/day in white mice did not determine the LD_{50} dose (Thanh et al. 2020), and *C. zedoaria* extract did not cause symptoms of toxicity and mortality in rats at a dose of 2,000 mg/kgP (Tandanu et al. 2022). A study presented that the LD_{50} of ethanolic extract of *H. sabdariffa* leaves was 850.90 mg/kgP (Sari et al. 2016). The ethanolic extract of *L. indica* leaves showed LC_{50} acute toxicity of 11.644 ppm (Duma et al. 2021).

Concerned to antihyperlipidemic activity experiments, hyperlipidemia, characterized by abnormally elevated serum TC, TG, LDL-C, and HDL-C, is an established risk factor in the development of coronary artery disease. In the present study, the effects of CHM-Lipid combination on serum lipid levels were evaluated in hyperlipidemic mice induced by P-407. P-407 has been utilized in the hyperlipidemic model due to its convenience, reproducibility, and the lack of undesirable underlying pathological conditions. P-407 is also well known to cause elevated serum TC, TG, and LDL-C levels in mice, which are important risk factors for atherosclerosis development (Johnston 2004). Our study showed the lipid profile of induced mice tremendously increased by more than 5 folds (TC), and 10 folds (TG) with a single dose injection of P-407 at 600 mg/kgP. The polyherbal combination CHM-Lipid at 500 mg/kgP/day dose significantly reduced elevated TC, TG, and LDL-C levels when compared to the control hyperlipidemic group. It supports the traditional claims of the product as an antihyperlipidaemic therapy.

The elevation of TC levels following P-407 i.p. injection to mice was due to stimulation of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-Co-enzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase activity in the liver by the poloxamer vehicle (Johnston 2004), the cholesterol-lowering effects of the CHM-Lipid combination might be due to the inhibition of hepatic HMG CoA reductase, the limiting enzyme rate in the cholesterol biosynthesis since atorvastatin which was used as a positive control in this study is an HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor. As P-407 directly inhibits capillary lipoprotein lipase (LPL) responsible for serum triacylglycerol hydrolysis to fatty acid, the increase in TG is mediated by P-407 ip. injection to mice results primarily from an inhibition of triacylglycerol degradation or inhibition of the synthesis of TG's from fatty acids (Fidèle et al. 2017).

The serum triacylglycerol lowering effect of the CHM-Lipid combination can be attributed to the ability of the formulation to increase the lipoprotein lipase activities. On the other hand, an increase in HDL-C considers the deceleration of the atherosclerotic process by preventing LDL-C oxidation, accelerating the catabolism of LDL-C to free up cholesterol for

steroid synthesis, and promoting the cholesterol translocation from peripheral tissue like arterial walls to the liver for catabolism. Decreasing the levels of LDL-C in serum is the target for several antihyperlipidaemic drugs used in conventional medicines (Fidèle et al. 2017).

Treatment of mice with either CHM-lipid at 500 mg/kgP dose or standard drug atorvastatin at 50 mg/kgP dose increased HDL-C level ($P < 0,05$). Although this increase was not significant in comparison with the induced without treatment controls, it is also a positive sign against hyperlipidemia by using plant-based products. Possibly, a longer treatment period study is needed to understand the antihyperlipidaemic effect of CHM-Lipid completely.

The study results also showed that at a higher dose of CHM-Lipid oral administration (1000 mg/kgP), the polyherbal combination did not significantly change the serum lipid profile in experimental mice ($P > 0,05$). Many medicinal plants have been found to have potential as antihyperlipidemic agents, and they do so through stimulation of thermogenesis, inhibition of pancreatic lipase activity, control of appetite, prevention of adipogenesis, and promotion of lipolysis (Dghaim et al. 2015). All the herbal components of the polyherbal formulation, CHM-Lipid, including *L. indica*, *C. zedoaria*, *H. sabdariffa*, *D. indica*, and *C. hindsii* have been shown to have antihyperlipidemic properties in published research. The ethanolic extract of *L. indica* leaves with 400 mg/kg b.w. dose had a positive effect on cholesterol levels in the serum lipid profile of HDL-cholesterol and LDL-cholesterol (Riris et al. 2022). The water extract of *C. zedoaria* rhizome showed a significant increase in HDL-C and a decrease in LDL-C after two months of consumption, presenting its protective role against hypercholesterolemic and lipidemic conditions (Tariq et al. 2016). The ethanolic extract from the leaves of *H. sabdariffa* with a dose of 300 mg/kgP exhibited a significant reduction in lipid levels of the hypolipidemic activity but was less effective than the standard drug, atorvastatin (Gosain et al. 2010).

The ethyl acetate extract fraction from *D. indica* fruits significantly attenuated TC by 10.3%, TA by 31.6 %, and LDL-C by 28.6% in obese mice (Loan et al. 2011). The methanolic extract of *C. paniculatus* at the optimized dose of 65 mg/kgP substantially reduced the TC, TG, and LDL-C (Patil et al. 2011). Many new herbal combinations have been studied as antihyperlipidemic medicines. A new polyherbal formulation containing hydroalcoholic extracts of four plants, namely *Salacia oblonga*, *Salacia roxbhurgii*, *Garcinia indica*, and *Lagerstroemia parviflora*, was tested in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats model, showed good antihyperglycemic and antihyperlipidemic properties at an oral dose of 400 mg/kgP and thus help in preventing future complications of diabetes (Subhasree et al. 2015).

Other new powdered polyherbal formulation containing *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Gymnema sylvestre*, *Acacia catechu*, and *Murraya koenigii* was standardized for treating hyperlipidemia (Rani et al. 2021). Our study of the CHM-Lipid combination and published results of its components on the antihyperlipidemic effects supported the antihyperlipidemic activity at a 500 mg/kgP dose in the P 407-induced mice model.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the present study demonstrated that the polyherbal preparation CHM-Lipid did not cause any death in experimental animals at 5,000 mg/kg body weight/day and belonged to the orally non-toxic herbal medicine. The polyherbal combination also exhibited noticeable antihyperlipidemic activity at a dose of 500 mg/kg body weight in the P 407-induced mice model. However, a longer treatment course study is needed for more sufficient effects.

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